

DELAMINATION IDENTIFICATION USING PIEZOELECTRIC SENSORS

Ning Hu and Hisao Fukunaga

*Department of Aeronautics and Space Engineering, Tohoku University, 01 Aramaki-Aoba, Aoba-ku,
Sendai 980-8579, Japan*

SUMMARY: The application of piezoelectric sensors in the damage identification has received much attention recently. In this research, a delamination identification method is proposed using piezoelectric sensors. First, a first-order approximate technique is proposed for obtaining the electrical potential change on sensors. Then, both numerical and experimental data in the time domain are transformed into the frequency domain. The damage or delamination location, then, can be detected by matching the numerical data and the experimental data through a detection technique. A beam example is used to illustrate the effectiveness of the present algorithm.

KEYWORDS : delamination, identification, piezoelectric sensors

INTRODUCTION

The development of a new class of “smart” materials and adaptive structures with sensory/active capabilities may improve the performance and reliability of aeronautical structural systems. Till now, the researches in the field of damage identification using piezoelectrics have been received much attention [1]. Many researches in this field have been focused on experimental investigation of the change in the data obtained from piezoelectrics due to damages and illustration of the possibility of damage identification [2]. Some authors have tried to detect the damages using the piezoelectric sensors. Keilers and Chang [3] have set up a numerical beam model at first and then employed it with experimental FRF data from an attached sensor to identify the delamination location randomly. Banks, Inman and Leo *et al.* [4] employed the time-domain data on sensors for locating the damages. Schulz *et al.* [5] have used the transmittance function method to locate the damages with multiple sensors. Further, some recent efforts have been focused on the application of Lamb wave for damage detection [6]. In this research, a damage identification method is proposed using limited number of piezoelectric sensors. First, a first-order approximate technique is proposed to obtain the electrical potential

change on sensors in the time domain. In order to detect the damage locations more easily, both numerical and experimental data in the time domain are transformed into the frequency domain. The damage locations can then be detected by matching the numerical data and the experimental data in the frequency domain through a proposed identification technique, which can separate the effects of damage severity and damage locations and eliminate the influence of damage severity for better detection of damage locations. A beam example is employed to illustrate the effectiveness of the present algorithm.

THEORY

Basic assumptions and system equations

The equation of a pre-damaged system can be described as follows

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_0 + \mathbf{K}^0 \mathbf{u}_0 = \mathbf{Q}, \quad \mathbf{f}_s^0 = -\mathbf{S}\mathbf{u}_0 \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{Q} represents the mechanical force or actuator force vector. Also, \mathbf{K}^0 and \mathbf{S} are expressed as follows [7],

$$\mathbf{K}^0 = \mathbf{K}_{uu}^0 - \mathbf{K}_{uf} \mathbf{K}_{ff}^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{fu} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{K}_{ff}^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{fu} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{S} matrix plays a role of computing electrical potentials \mathbf{f}_s^0 on sensors from the displacements \mathbf{u}_0 .

The equation of a damaged system can also be cast into the following similar form

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_1 + (\mathbf{K}^0 + \Delta\mathbf{K})\mathbf{u}_1 = \mathbf{Q}, \quad \mathbf{f}_s^1 = -\mathbf{S}\mathbf{u}_1 \quad (3)$$

where damages are considered as a perturbation of the stiffness matrix, i.e. $\Delta\mathbf{K}$. For the sake of simplicity, the damping and mass change due to damages are neglected.

From eqns (1) and (3), it can be seen that the task is to search for the damage location by analyzing the difference between \mathbf{f}_s^0 and \mathbf{f}_s^1 . Generally, the response of the damaged structures is a nonlinear function of the damage locations and damage extents, i.e. $\mathbf{f}_s^1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{P})$, where \mathbf{a} is the damage extent and \mathbf{P} the vector representing the damage positions. For the sake of simplicity, here the effect of the damage extent is simplified by a scalar \mathbf{a} . We try to separate the influences of two parameters in order to search for the damage location more easily. Performing the Taylor expansion of $\mathbf{f}_s^1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{P})$ to \mathbf{a} leads to

$$\mathbf{f}_s^1(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{P}) \approx \mathbf{f}_s^0 + \mathbf{a}\mathbf{A}_1(\mathbf{P}) + \mathbf{a}^2\mathbf{A}_2(\mathbf{P}) + \Lambda \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_1, \mathbf{A}_2 \dots$ are only functions of damage locations.

This is the fundamental assumption in this research, i.e. the effects of the damage extents and damage locations can be separated approximately. This assumption is reasonable for some damage patterns [8,9]. From eqn (4), the electrical potential change can be expressed as,

$$\Delta\mathbf{f}_s(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{P}) \approx \mathbf{a}\mathbf{A}_1(\mathbf{P}) + \mathbf{a}^2\mathbf{A}_2(\mathbf{P}) + \Lambda \quad (5)$$

A technique for damage detection is proposed later to eliminate the influence of \mathbf{a} when only the first-order approximation is used.

First-order approximation

Employing the modal superposition method, the transient response $\mathbf{u}_0(t)$ of the pre-damaged system can be expanded as:

$$\mathbf{u}_0(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{j}_i(\mathbf{x}) x_i^0(t) \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{x} denotes the spatial position and re-writing eqn (1a) in the modal space results into

$$\ddot{\mathbf{x}}_i^0(t) + \mathbf{w}_i^2 x_i^0(t) = \mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{Q}(t) \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{j}_i and \mathbf{w}_i are the mode and frequency of the intact structure, i.e. $\mathbf{K}^0 \mathbf{j}_i = \mathbf{w}_i^2 \mathbf{M} \mathbf{j}_i$. In derivation of eqn (7), the following conditions are employed although the normalization requirements may be unnecessary in the present approach,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{K}^0 \mathbf{j}_i &= \mathbf{w}_i^2, \quad \mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{K}^0 \mathbf{j}_j = 0 \quad (i \neq j), \\ \mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{M} \mathbf{j}_i &= 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{M} \mathbf{j}_j = 0 \quad (i \neq j) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Under condition of the harmonic input of $\mathbf{Q}(t)$, especially for the case of sinusoidal input, i.e. $\mathbf{p} \sin(\mathbf{w}_f t)$, where \mathbf{p} vector denotes the positions of loads and the amplitude of loads, eqn (7) can be solved from Duhamel's integral for zero initial conditions as follows

$$x_i^0(t) = \frac{\mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{p}}{\mathbf{w}_i} \int_0^t \sin(\mathbf{w}_f \mathbf{t}) \sin \mathbf{w}_i(t - \mathbf{t}) d\mathbf{t} = \frac{\mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{p}}{\mathbf{w}_i} F_i(t) \quad (9)$$

where the integral $F_i(t)$ can be described in the following form,

$$F_i(t) = \frac{-\sin(\mathbf{w}_f t) \mathbf{w}_i + \sin(\mathbf{w}_i t) \mathbf{w}_f}{(\mathbf{w}_f + \mathbf{w}_i)(\mathbf{w}_f - \mathbf{w}_i)} \quad (10)$$

Furthermore, eqn (3a) can also be expanded in the modal space as follows

$$\ddot{\mathbf{x}}_i^1(t) + \bar{\mathbf{w}}_i^2 x_i^1(t) = \bar{\mathbf{j}}_i^T \mathbf{Q}(t) \quad (11)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{w}}_i$ and $\bar{\mathbf{j}}_i$ are the natural frequency and mode of the damaged structure. The transient response of eqn (11) is

$$x_i^1(t) = \frac{\bar{\mathbf{j}}_i^T \mathbf{p}}{\bar{\mathbf{w}}_i} \int_0^t \sin(\mathbf{w}_f \mathbf{t}) \sin \bar{\mathbf{w}}_i(t - \mathbf{t}) d\mathbf{t} \quad (12)$$

The above equation is obviously nonlinear. By employing the following perturbations

$$\bar{\mathbf{w}}_i = \mathbf{w}_i + \Delta \mathbf{w}_i, \quad \bar{\mathbf{j}}_i = \mathbf{j}_i + \Delta \mathbf{j}_i \quad (13)$$

and neglecting the higher-order terms, such as $(\Delta \mathbf{w}_i / \mathbf{w}_i)^2$, $(\Delta \mathbf{j}_i^T)^2$ and $(\Delta \mathbf{j}_i^T \Delta \mathbf{w}_i / \mathbf{w}_i)$, eqn (12) can be approximated as

$$x_i^1(t) \approx \frac{\mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{p}}{\mathbf{w}_i} F_i(t) + \frac{\Delta \mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{p}}{\mathbf{w}_i} F_i(t) + \frac{\mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{p}}{\mathbf{w}_i} F_i'(t) \left(\frac{\Delta \mathbf{w}_i}{\mathbf{w}_i} \right) \quad (14)$$

where

$$F_i'(t) = - \frac{\sin(\mathbf{w}_f t) \mathbf{w}_i (\mathbf{w}_f^2 + \mathbf{w}_i^2)}{(\mathbf{w}_f^4 - 2\mathbf{w}_f^2 \mathbf{w}_i^2 + \mathbf{w}_i^4)} + \frac{\mathbf{w}_f \mathbf{w}_i [\cos(\mathbf{w}_i t) (\mathbf{w}_f^2 - \mathbf{w}_i^2) + 2 \sin(\mathbf{w}_i t) \mathbf{w}_i]}{(\mathbf{w}_f^4 - 2\mathbf{w}_f^2 \mathbf{w}_i^2 + \mathbf{w}_i^4)} + \frac{\sin(\mathbf{w}_f t) \mathbf{w}_i - \mathbf{w}_f \sin(\mathbf{w}_i t)}{(\mathbf{w}_f + \mathbf{w}_i)(\mathbf{w}_f - \mathbf{w}_i)} \quad (15)$$

The displacements of the damaged structure can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{u}_1(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{J}_i(\mathbf{x}) x_i^1(t) \quad (16)$$

From eqns (6), (9), (14) and (16), the displacement change caused by the damages is

$$\Delta \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}_0 - \mathbf{u}_1 \approx \sum_{i=1}^N \left[-\Delta \mathbf{j}_i \frac{\mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{p}}{\mathbf{w}_i} F_i(t) - \mathbf{j}_i \frac{\Delta \mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{p}}{\mathbf{w}_i} F_i(t) - \mathbf{j}_i \frac{\mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{p}}{\mathbf{w}_i} F_i'(t) \left(\frac{\Delta \mathbf{w}_i}{\mathbf{w}_i} \right) \right] \quad (17)$$

The above equation is the most important formulation in this research. In fact, this equation relates the changes of transient responses in the time domain, i.e. the left-hand side, and the modal data, i.e. the right-hand side. In the right-hand side, the first two terms represent the parts of displacement changes caused by the vibration mode variation. The third term represents the part of displacement changes caused by the natural frequency changes. Furthermore, by observing eqn (10), it can be found that $F_i(t)$ is a harmonic function. Then, in eqn (17), the influences of the vibration mode variation on the transient response, i.e. the first two terms of the right-hand side are harmonic. However, inspection of eqn (15) shows that $F_i'(t)$ is not a harmonic function obviously by seeing the second term in eqn (15). Therefore, in eqn (17), the influences of the natural frequency changes on the transient response, i.e. the third term, will be amplified with the increase of time. Actually, as stated later, the influence of the third term on transient responses are much more significant than those of the first two terms. Furthermore, the above closed-form equation makes the computation cost very low.

Following Stetson's work [12], the first-order perturbation is used to relate $\Delta \mathbf{w}_i$ and $\Delta \mathbf{j}_i$ with $\Delta \mathbf{K}$. Under condition of stiffness variation only, the changes in natural frequencies and modes can be described as follows

$$\Delta \mathbf{w}_i \approx \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta k_i}{\mathbf{w}_i} \right), \quad \Delta \mathbf{j}_i = \sum_{j=1}^M \frac{k_{ij}}{(\mathbf{w}_i^2 - \mathbf{w}_j^2)} \mathbf{j}_j, \quad i \neq j \quad (18)$$

where

$$\Delta k_i = \mathbf{j}_i^T \Delta \mathbf{K} \mathbf{j}_i, \quad \Delta k_{ij} = \mathbf{j}_i^T \Delta \mathbf{K} \mathbf{j}_j \quad (19)$$

Equation (18b) is only suitable for problems in which there are different natural frequencies. If there is a multiple root in a system, the mode change relating to this root is indefinite. We will discuss this problem later.

Finally, from eqns (1a), (17) and (18), the potential change can be expressed as

$$\Delta f_s \approx \mathbf{S} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^N \left[- \sum_{j=1}^M \frac{\mathbf{j}_i^T \Delta \mathbf{K} \mathbf{j}_j}{(\mathbf{w}_i^2 - \mathbf{w}_j^2) \mathbf{w}_i} \mathbf{j}_j \mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{p} F_i(t) - \sum_{j=1}^M \frac{\mathbf{j}_i^T \Delta \mathbf{K} \mathbf{j}_j}{(\mathbf{w}_i^2 - \mathbf{w}_j^2) \mathbf{w}_i} \mathbf{j}_i \mathbf{j}_j^T \mathbf{p} F_i(t) - \frac{\mathbf{j}_i^T \Delta \mathbf{K} \mathbf{j}_i}{2\mathbf{w}_i^3} \mathbf{j}_i \mathbf{j}_i^T \mathbf{p} F_i(t) \right] \right\}, \quad i \neq j \quad (20)$$

Identification technique for damage location

When using the finite element method, the stiffness change $\Delta \mathbf{K}$ in system can be expressed as the summation of the changes in elemental stiffness matrices as follows,

$$\Delta \mathbf{K} = \sum_{i=1}^{ND} \mathbf{B}_i^T \Delta \mathbf{k}_i^* \mathbf{B}_i \quad (21)$$

Here ND is the number of damaged elements, \mathbf{B}_i is the Boolean matrix of the i th element and $\Delta \mathbf{k}_i^*$ is the stiffness change of the i th element, which can be further expressed as

$$\Delta \mathbf{k}_i^* = \mathbf{a}_i E_i \Delta \mathbf{k}_i \quad (22)$$

where \mathbf{a}_i is a scalar denoting the damage fraction or damage extent in stiffness ($-1.0 \leq \mathbf{a}_i \leq 0.0$) and E_i is a parameter representing the undamaged stiffness property in element i (e.g. the Young's modulus). The matrix $\Delta \mathbf{k}_i$ involves only geometric quantities or terms containing the Poisson's ratio probably. For structures with single damage or multiple damages with the same severity, the scalar \mathbf{a}_i can be extracted from the equation (represented by \mathbf{a}) for separating the influence of damage extent and damage location. Finally, the electrical potential change on the l th sensor, i.e. $\Delta \mathbf{f}_s^l(t)$ can be calculated from eqn (20) using eqns (21) and (22).

If we assume that the damage exists in only one element, i.e. $ND=1$, the comparison between the numerical estimation in eqn (20) and the experimental results $\Delta \mathbf{f}_s^{*l}(t)$ in the time domain can be carried out one element by one element sequentially. However, as investigated later numerically, this comparison can be performed more effectively when transforming the data from the discrete time domain to the frequency domain using the following FFT,

$$\Delta \Phi_s^l[k] = \sum_{n=0}^{L-1} \Delta \mathbf{f}_s^l[n] w[n] e^{-j \frac{2\pi}{L} k \cdot n} \quad (23)$$

where $w[n]$ is a window function to eliminate the effects of discontinuity.

Therefore, the different quantities obtained from the FFT can be employed for damage identification, here the spectrum radius, i.e. $\|\text{Re}(\Delta \mathbf{F}_s^l) + j \text{Im}(\Delta \mathbf{F}_s^l)\|$ is used, which is also

represented by ΔF_s^l thereafter for simplicity. Because we can only compare the similarity or likelihood between two curves of different amplitudes in the frequency domain, the following normalized correlation of the scale invariance is defined

$$r(\Delta F_s^l, \Delta F_s^{l*}) = \frac{\Delta F_s^l \bullet \Delta F_s^{l*}}{\|\Delta F_s^l\| \|\Delta F_s^{l*}\|} \quad (24)$$

where ΔF_s^l and ΔF_s^{l*} are vectors with components $\Delta F_s^l(f_j)$ and $\Delta F_s^{l*}(f_j)$ and $\Delta F_s^l(f_j)$ is obtained from eqn (20) by assuming one damaged element in structure. When the above correlation is close to 1, then two vectors are very similar. The possibility of the occurrence of damage in the corresponding element is high. From eqn (22), it can be seen that \mathbf{a} can be eliminated in eqn (24). Then, eqn (24) does not relate with the damage extent except the damage location information. Setting the number of sensors NSE for comparison, for the i th element, the following equation is employed

$$E_i = \sum_{l=1}^{NSE} |1 - r_i(\Delta F_s^l |_i, \Delta F_s^{l*})| \quad (25)$$

where $\Delta F_s^l |_i$ is the numerically generated data when assuming the damage in the i th element.

The possible damage location in the structure is indicated by the smallest discrepancy calculated from eqn (25). The following parameter D_i is defined for element i as: $D_i=1/E_i$. The largest one of D_i corresponds to the possible damaged member. Therefore, the following damage index is finally defined for element i

$$DAM_i = \frac{D_i}{\text{MAX}(D_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, NE)} \quad (26)$$

where NE is number of elements in structure.

The above identification procedure can also be employed in the time domain.

It should be noted that the FRF data here are different from the usual FRF data of other authors [4] from several respects. First, here the FFT is performed on the data of the electrical potential change in the time domain. Therefore, the obtained data in the frequency domain contains the integrated modal information of both intact and damaged structures. Then it includes the information of the changes in natural frequencies and modes due to the damages. Second, for a prescribed excitation frequency of external forces, the present data contains the information of those modal data whose natural frequencies are close to the excitation frequency. However, in the usual FRF under harmonic excitation, it contains the information of one frequency point only. Third, to obtain the usual FRF curves numerically, one should scan over the whole frequency domain where he is interested. Then it is very computationally expensive. However, only the analysis of the transient response using eqn (20) and one FFT analysis are needed here, whose computational cost is very low. Further, in the present technique, the sufficient long sampling time domain should be taken in order to guarantee the

accuracy of the FFT and include the sufficient modal data. Our experiences have shown that the time domain should be at least taken up to $T_1=1/f_1$ for obtaining stable results in the frequency domain, where f_1 is the fundamental frequency of structures.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

A beam shown in Fig. 1 is employed. The materials constants of composite plate of 0° plies only are listed as: $E_{11}=142.0$ GPa, $E_{22}=10.3$ GPa, $G_{12}=G_{13}=7.2$ GPa, $G_{23}=4.29$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=0.25$ and $\rho=1382.1$ kg/m³. The mechanical and piezoelectric properties of the PVDF sensors are: $E_{11}=E_{22}=2.0$ GPa, $G_{12}=G_{13}=G_{23}=0.8$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=\nu_{23}=\nu_{13}=0.25$, $d_{31}=-154.0$ pm/V, $d_{32}=0.0$ pm/V, $p_{33}=0.1505 \cdot 10^{-9}$ F/m and $\rho=1300.0$ kg/m³. Only the bending deformation in the x -axis direction is considered. A 9-node finite element using a higher-order plate theory [9] is employed. The frequency of 3 identical concentrated external forces, i.e. ω_f is 22000 (Hz), which is located between the third and fourth natural frequencies of the beam. The amplitude of the concentrated forces is 50 N. The time increment step is $2\mu s$, and N and M in eqn (20) for modal superposition are 50. The damage is assumed to occur at the element 3. Two kinds of damage models are investigated. One is the so-called uniform damage, i.e. the same reduction ratio in various elastic module. This model is usually suitable for modelling the transverse crack in beam. Another is the delamination, i.e. in-plane crack, which exists at the mid-plane of the element 3. First, the uniform damage is used for investigating the present approach.

Discussion on accuracy of the first order approximation

To check the accuracy of the first-order approximation, the central deflection change of the beam is employed as shown in Fig. 2. In this figure, two first-order approximation approaches are employed. FODA1 denotes that all three terms are used in eqn (17) and FODA2 denotes that only the third term in eqn (17) is used. Inspection of this figure reveals that the first-order approximation has quite high accuracy. From our numerical experience, for the damage extent over 50%, the accuracy of the first-order approximation decreases. The accuracy of FODA2 is only a little lower than that of FODA1 within an initial time period. Therefore, compared with the effect of natural frequency changes, the contribution from the vibration mode changes is small. In fact, many other authors, such as Armon *et al.* [11] also found that mode shapes almost remain unchanged by the small change in stiffness. Then, for the structures with multiple roots, the vibration mode changes of these roots are indefinite. In this case, two procedures can be taken simultaneously. One is to choose the external force frequency to be far from multiple roots since the structural transient response is mainly dominated by the modal data of the natural frequencies, which are close to the external force frequency. Another is that, in the first two terms of eqn (17), the contribution of the changes in vibration modes of multiple roots is neglected only, but the contribution of the changes in vibration modes of single roots is kept. Furthermore, in the third term, the contribution of all modes should be considered.

Fig. 1 Geometry of a beam with sensors Fig. 2 Comparison of central deflection change

Fig. 3(a) Detection result using sensor 1 Fig. 3(b) Detection result using sensor 8

Fig. 4(a) Detection result using sensor 1 Fig. 4(b) Detection result using sensor 8

Results of damage location identification (uniform damage)

In this computation, the frequency of the external forces w_f is chosen to be 3000 (Hz), which is lower than the 1st natural frequency. When using eqn (26), the frequency domain is taken from -6840 Hz to 6840 Hz. 29 sampling points within this frequency domain are used. The

Fig. 5. Detection results using sensor 1 (delamination)

damage detection results for 10% damage case are illustrated in Fig. 3 when using the data of sensor 1 and sensor 8, independently. Also, Blackman window function is employed in FFT. Figure 3 shows that the damage location can be detected successfully. For other sensors, the damage can also be detected clearly. We also computed eqn (26) in the time domain. It was found that the results become worse. When the damage extent in element 3 is up to 50%, the identification results are shown in Fig. 4. Inspection of it reveals that the results become a little worse due to the errors in the first-order approximation. Furthermore, to investigate the influence of the frequency of external forces, we calculated the damage detection results using various excitation frequencies. We found that the present algorithm is not sensitive to the frequency of the external forces although the better results can be obtained when the frequency of the external forces is around or even lower than the first order of natural frequency in the present example.

Results of damage location identification (delamination)

The frequency of external forces, i.e. w_f is 3000 (Hz). Our previous FEM (9-node element) [9] is used to generate the simulated experimental data with fine meshes on delamination section. Finally a coarse mesh with 8 elements is used for delamination detection. The results using the data of sensor 1 only are shown in Fig. 5 for DAM_i . From this figure, it can be found that the delamination section can be identified although the results become worse. The most important reason for this phenomenon may be due to the simplified damage model (scalar damage extents) used in eqn (22), which cannot express the influence of the in-plane crack, i.e. delamination sufficiently. Therefore, more detailed damage model should be used to describe the effect of delaminations for achieving the better identification results.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a damage identification method using the limited number of piezoelectric

sensors has been proposed. First, a first-order approximate technique is proposed for obtaining the transient response of the electrical potential change on sensors. After the FFT of the numerical and experimental data from the time domain to the frequency domain, an identification technique is proposed by matching the numerical data and the experimental data. A beam example is employed to illustrate the effectiveness of the present algorithm. From the numerical example, it was found that the damage can be detected effectively when assuming the uniform damage pattern. However, for the delamination (anisotropic damage), the detection results become worse although the damage location can also be found successfully.

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